

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-6
MANAGEMENT ETHICS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Kazakbaeva Dilfuza

Nukus is a DPI student

Abstract: The average age of employees in an organization led by a young leader is often low. Youth (around 30-35 years old) is characterized by a tendency to innovation and discovery, creativity, fearlessness and adaptability to a changing environment.

Key words: leader, youth, pedagogue, management ethics, method.

The effectiveness of the management of educational institutions directly depends on the leaders. During the years of independence, a lot of work was done in the field of strengthening educational institutions with qualified leaders. However, this problem is still serious in higher education, university, secondary and vocational education institutions. The process of training an army of competent, trained leaders requires a complex and long period and a complex approach to this field. That's why it is necessary to direct all managers working in higher education, post-secondary, secondary and vocational education institutions to specific goals, it is necessary to form a patriotic leader of our independent Republic on the basis of national and universal values, and to educate and improve the best qualities of national pride and national character in them.

Image - (eng. image - image, image) is a specific synthetic image that appears in the minds of people in relation to a specific person, organization or other social object, embodies information about the perceived object and encourages social behavior. .

Creating the image of a modern leader is his face, clothes, heart, sound mind, behavior culture, a person who perfectly masters the art of management, competence: knowledge, thinking, professional skills, wisdom, human qualities such as modesty, politeness, beauty, morality, teaching and learning, relying on the traditions of the teacher and the student, is to raise the authority of a person, to increase his reputation, to be respected. Means: verbal, kinetic, visual.

Napoleon said: "Those who cannot hold their speech cannot be leaders." A leader must know how to speak in front of an audience, whether he is a partner or a subordinate.

The average age of employees in an organization led by a young leader is often low. Youth (around 30-35 years old) is characterized by a tendency to innovation and discovery, creativity, fearlessness and adaptability to a changing environment. Unfortunately, in such an organization, older employees (over 40-45) are even looked at with suspicion. However, it was found that a person becomes a skilled master of his profession at the age of 35-55, acquires knowledge in his field well, and feels eager to introduce inventions. At the same time, a cold analysis of the situation, a mood of restraint is formed.

Of course, it is difficult to say that all young leaders are supporters of advanced technology and are inclined to it, but modernity is characteristic of young people. This, in turn, increases the possibility of the young leader to turn to modern and advanced

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-6

production methods. There is a saying in our people that old is still young. Therefore, a modern leader, regardless of his age, should be a supporter of advanced technologies and capable of introducing modern production at the organization level. This is a transitional requirement. Gender of leader. The human race requires him to follow the same role. This situation is especially evident in the conditions of eastern countries and our region. In this area, male and female sexual social norms are clearly defined. As long as it is so, most of the actions performed by a person are perceived under the influence of this sex role criterion. Now, regardless of a person's gender, we see that great opportunities are emerging in the profession or position. In our country, a great way has been opened for women in the field of entrepreneurship and public administration. But, despite this, the word "leader" is often expressed by the male gender, and for some reason, it does not go beyond the spheres managed by a female leader, including education, health care, and public services.

Various methods are used to determine the socio-psychological knowledge of a person, first of all, a leader. These are the methods of determining the communicative qualities of many people we know. But most of them are not suitable for carrying out diagnostic work from a theoretical point of view. Among all methodological methods, precisely the KOS-1 method, which determines the ability of a person to influence others by being able to quickly and accurately work with others and establish personal communication, is gaining more and more confidence among researchers. The convenience of the method is that it does not take much time (10-15 minutes) and requires the respondent to answer "yes" or "no" to 40 questions.

Social-psychological competence is related not only to self-awareness (knowledge) of the leader, but also to auto-psychological competence. [4] Self-psychological competence is a set of skills of a manager, which enable the manager to diagnose his professional and personal qualities, i.e. self-diagnosis, self-correction (correction), self-improvement, self-motivation, effective use of any information are abilities related to psycholinguistic competencies. [5] Socio-information competence is the ability of a leader to work with information technologies and to have a critical attitude towards social information. [6] Communicative competence is a manager's mastery of oral and written communication technologies in different languages and the ability to communicate via computer programming and the Internet. The concept of socio-psychological competence is often used by some experts as a synonym for the concept of "communicative competence" in the media. In order to determine direct communicative competence, a number of methods such as "Level of accessibility to communication", "Ability to express an opinion" and a special test of M. Snyder are used to find out how much one can control oneself. [7] Cognitive competence means the leader's readiness to increase the level of information, the need to activate his personal capabilities, the ability to independently create new skills and knowledge, and self-development. [8] Special competence is the manager's ability to prepare to perform professional actions independently and to be able to evaluate the results of his work. [9] Cultural competence is a manager's willingness to guide his or her behavior through organizational norms and values. Also, the ability to

VOLUME-3, ISSUE-6

maintain standard situations and replace them with new ones if necessary to achieve a goal in inappropriate situations.

References:

1. Muxiddinov A.G. O'quv jarayonida nutq faoliyati. – T.: O'qituvchi, 1995.
2. Pedagogik kompetentlik va kreativlik asoslari / Muslimov N.A., Usmonboeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., To'raev A.B. – T.: "Sano standart" nashriyoti, 2015.
3. Amina, T. (2022). TA'LIMDA PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(7), 4-5.
4. Amina, T. (2021, December). The Importance of Daily Life Programs in the Karakalpak Language. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 285-288).
5. Djurakulova, G. S. (2020). Epic formulas associated with the horse in the Uzbek folk epic. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (92), 207-210.
6. Djurakulova, G. S. (2020). Эпические формулы, связанные с лошадью в узбекском народном эпосе. Theoretical & Applied Science, (12), 207-210.
7. Djurakulova, G. S. (2019). Uzbek folklore traditions and his presence. Научные горизонты, (8), 3-7.
8. Norov, I., Yo'ldoshev, J., & Yo'ldoshev, S. (2023). ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA DARS TASHKIL QILISH. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RECENTLY SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHER'S THEORY, 1(4), 40-47.